

COST-EFFECTIVENESS OF SEASONAL INFLUENZA VACCINATION PROPHYLAXIS**Zlatanova T.**

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ABSTRACT

Influenza remains one of the world's greatest public health challenges. Each year, there are about 1 billion cases worldwide, of which 3 to 5 million are severe, resulting in 290,000 to 650,000 flu-related deaths. All of this results in great costs for those affected as well as for the health system and society as a whole. This article presents an analysis of influenza morbidity and costs associated with treatment. The article also contains data on the coverage for seasonal influenza immunization. Based on an analysis of the data presented, we concluded that seasonal influenza vaccination is the only effective and inexpensive means of preventing new influenza epidemics and reducing treatment costs for the health systems and the population.

Keywords: vaccine prophylaxis, influenza, morbidity, cost, effectiveness, epidemic.

INTRODUCTION

Influenza persists as one of the world's greatest challenges to public health. Each year, there are about 1 billion cases worldwide, of which 3 to 5 million are severe, resulting in 290,000 to 650,000 flu-related deaths. The most effective way to prevent the disease, recommended by the WHO, is annual influenza vaccination. Vaccination is particularly important for people at higher risk of severe complications from influenza and for health professionals (WHO launches new global influenza strategy, <https://www.zdrave.net/n8930> accessed 06.11.2024).

The goal of this paper is to present the cost-effectiveness of vaccination prophylaxis in influenza season.

To achieve this goal, we have set ourselves the following tasks:

1. An analysis of the morbidity and hospitalization rates of non-immunized and immunized persons based on the available literature.
2. An analysis of seasonal influenza vaccine coverage in Europe and Bulgaria.

To achieve this goal, we have used a documentary method, analyzing regulatory documents, WHO reports and available literature sources related to vaccination and seasonal influenza spread.

ANALYSIS

Influenza epidemics cause economic losses, both direct (hospitalisation, outpatient care, doctor visits) and indirect (temporary disability, strain on health and insurance services), and suffering for patients (A. Galev, 2020).

A WHO report states that the global influenza strategy for the 2019-2030 period provides for the prevention of seasonal influenza, as well as the control of

the virus' spread from animals to humans and the preparation for the next influenza pandemic. The world has experienced several deadly influenza pandemics, the worst being the Spanish Flu, which killed tens of millions in 1918. Other pandemics have followed since - in 1957, 1968 and 2009, when the H1N1 virus caused 18 500 deaths in 241 countries (<https://novini.bg/zdrave/bolesti/528393>).

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, in the USA during the 2019/2020 season, seasonal influenza vaccination prevented 7.5 million influenza cases, 3.7 million influenza-related physician consultations, 105,000 influenza-related hospitalizations, and 6,300 deaths resulting from influenza.

In another study conducted in 2018, again among adults hospitalized due to influenza, the results showed that vaccinated patients were 59% less likely to be admitted to an intensive care unit compared to unvaccinated patients. Vaccinated patients treated in an intensive care unit stay 4 days less than unvaccinated patients

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264410X18309976?via%3Dihub>).

The long-standing influenza tracking system in Bulgaria shows that annual influenza epidemics are a serious health problem faced by our country. On average, around 1 400 000 to 1 600 000 cases of acute respiratory illness (ARIs) and influenza occur in regional cities alone each year, and they account for 10 to 30% of all temporary disability cases. These data demonstrate that annual influenza epidemics are the cause of serious economic loss stemming from both home and hospital treatment costs and unrealised social product due to the massive impact on individuals of working age.

Influenza cases are mainly clustered within 3 - 4 weeks. During these weeks, the national average morbidity rate reaches over 300 per 10 000 people, which means that at least 250 000 - 300 000 people were ill during the epidemic upsurge.

In the majority of cases, costs arising from a disease are calculated by adding together all direct, indirect and non-material costs. Direct costs arise from the use of medical and non-medical resources. Indirect costs are caused by productivity loss and absenteeism, while non-material costs are associated with reduced job performance and reduced quality of life. Direct costs are influenced by chronic comorbidities and other risk factors (e.g. age), which can lead to an increase in hospitalizations and longer treatment periods.

Seasonal influenza immunization coverage of patients at risk of serious complications, healthcare workers and healthy individuals in Europe is extremely varied (A. Galev, 2020). The UK and the Netherlands have well-established guidelines that are updated on a regular basis. They are also the countries with the best vaccination coverage (only these two European countries are close to the target of 75% coverage among the elderly). A European Commission report identified the need to improve seasonal influenza vaccination coverage and prevention policies in other European countries. According to this report, all Member States should take further action to maximise the benefits of seasonal influenza vaccination across Europe. The data from Bulgaria show that influenza vaccination coverage has been exceptionally low - below or slightly above 3% of the population over the past few years.

In accordance with Ordinance No. 15 of 2005 on immunization in the Republic of Bulgaria, immunization against influenza in the country is recommended and is carried out at the expense of the patients. Immunization against seasonal influenza is recommended annually for all persons 65 years of age and older, and for adults and children over 6 months of age who have chronic conditions.

As stated in the National Programme for Improving the Vaccination of Seasonal Influenza and Pneumococcal Infections in Persons Aged 65 Years and Older 2023-2026 in our country, influenza vaccines have the potential to prevent severe courses and mortality from influenza. Vaccinated patients are 26% less likely to be admitted to an intensive care unit and 31% less likely to die from influenza compared to those who are not vaccinated, according to a 2021 study of adults hospitalized for influenza (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0264410X21005624?dgcid=author>).

In Bulgaria, immunization coverage with seasonal influenza vaccines is low, with an average coverage of only 2.4 per 100 people (2.17-2.61%) for the 2013-2017 period (based on vaccine sales).

With the introduction of the National Seasonal Influenza Vaccine Improvement Program, 2019-2022, the following influenza immunization coverage in persons aged 65 years and above, who are the target group

of the program, has been achieved: 2019 - 7.8%, 2020 - 11.4% and 2021 - 13.24%.

As of 14.10.2024, 86 460 persons aged 65 and over have been vaccinated against influenza free of charge, under the National Programme for Improving the Vaccination of Seasonal Influenza and Pneumococcal Infections. 348 000 vaccine doses have been distributed under the National Programme for Improving the Vaccination of Seasonal Influenza and Pneumococcal Infections in Persons Aged 65 Years (<https://plusmen.bg/bg/facts/news/50>).

CONCLUSION

Influenza constitutes a significant socio-economic burden on society in terms of medical treatment (increased number of consultations, hospitalizations, clinical complications, use of medicines) and work absenteeism. There are different estimates of the overall economic impact of an influenza epidemic. So, for example, the total impact of an influenza epidemic (total estimated direct and indirect costs) in industrialised countries could be as high as €56.7 million per one million people. Seasonal influenza vaccines are the only effective and inexpensive measure for preventing new influenza epidemics and reducing the treatment costs to both the health systems and the population.

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